

Physical Studios & Digital Research Environments The Open Innovation Research Infrastructure (OI-RI) in a nutshell

Eveline Wandl-Vogt

Currently, vast amounts of fundings are invested in the development of digital research infrastructures. It has been documented, that especially in the arts and humanities the use of research infrastructures still is comparable low. On the other hand it is proven fact, that the use of infrastructures increases research output, productivity and innovation, which led to the development of scientific gateways, especially in the sciences. Critically reflecting the technology driven development of current research infrastructures, the author detects a lack of satisfaction when trying to apply research infrastructures into multidisciplinary, innovative, collaborative processes. Mainly, they miss to support methods as well as stay flexible against the dynamics of innovative, creative research processes, trying to involve researchers just at the end of an existing process and when products already developed, e.g. via user involvement, actually rather to disseminate an infrastructure than to build one.

Due to this unsatisfactory situation - especially, but not exclusively, in an experimental, (organisational) agile project design setting - , an international European consortium coordinated by the Austrian Academy of Sciences developed the concept of an Open Innovation Research Infrastructure (OI-RI) in 2017.

Core ideas of the infrastructure are: OI-RI is applying the liquidity concept on infrastructures. Next to a virtual environment, physical spaces and places are connected; a tight network of exchanging champions and knowledge is established. The OI-RI is aiming to support the implementation of the Knowledge for Development Agenda (2017).

OI-RI aims to stimulate and support the application of open innovation methods and practices in science to build an expert culture based upon openness and trust in value based organisational settings. It builds on the principles of co-design, participation and design thinking, developing infrastructures when, where and how they are needed in certain communities. The OI-RI is a innovation driven infrastructure. Innovation is interpreted socially and technically. It aims to bring together the right persons, knowledge and technologies to solve a question/problem; curiosity driven research as well as challenge driven processes are supported. The OI-RI is a flexible, "liquid", steadily developing environment; demonstrators are value driven organisational settings within the infrastructure; they are framing a collaborative innovation network. Scenarios are smaller organisational units, building best case examples. The concept was first established on the example of a cultural diversity demonstrator, aimed to connect the European Scientific Academies (AGATE ecosystem). Since then, it has been applied theoretically to various research areas, such as 1) biodiversity and linguistic diversity; 2) biographies; 3) media arts and 4) Lexicography.

Based on the visual representation the author aims to give a brief overview on the main mechanisms and challenge discussion to improve the concept.

keywords:

open innovation in science; impact science; human centered approach; liquidity; methodological infrastructure; hybrid infrastructure